

"USING MODERN INNOVATION IN THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM".

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Annotation: *This article provides information on "Using modern innovations in the modern education system."*

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Innovative educational technology is a set of teaching and learning techniques that include new or qualitative improvements in existing methods and tools to increase the efficiency of the learning process and create the best conditions for teaching and learning activities. methodology of organization of lim activities. current trends in the socio-economic development of society. Innovations in education include a set of measures aimed at the emergence of innovations in education. These innovations can be methods and techniques of organizing the educational process, resources used in the process of education and upbringing, scientific theories and concepts. Innovation develops through the use of research activities aimed at obtaining new scientific knowledge, some discoveries, inventions. In addition, the emergence of innovations can be the result of design work, which develops instrumental and technological knowledge that reflects the ability to make practical actions based on existing scientific theories and concepts. Thus, innovative projects are created, which then leads to the emergence of new technologies. Innovations also develop in the process of educational activities. In the learning process, students develop theoretical and practical knowledge, which can then be applied in various areas of practical life related to the creation of innovations. Innovative educational technologies are based on three main components: Modern, well-structured content, the basis of which is the competence in professional activity that meets the current realities of entrepreneurial activity. content includes a variety of multimedia materials transmitted through modern means of communication. Use of modern, innovative teaching methods. Such methods should be aimed at developing the competencies of the future specialist, involving students in

active knowledge and practical activities, showing initiative in the learning process. Passive assimilation of educational programs is excluded. Availability of modern infrastructure in the educational process. It should be based on the information, technological, organizational and communication components that help to apply new forms and methods of teaching, in particular distance learning. Innovative technologies in education are applied on the basis of the application of certain approaches in teaching, ie. principles that include the requirements and objectives that form the basis for the development of new technologies. All innovations in the field of pedagogy are based on strict compliance with the current stage of socio-economic development of society. At present, they should focus on developing students' independence, forming self-study and self-development skills, and mastering curricula consciously rather than mechanically. Innovative technologies in the field of education are constantly evolving and their range is expanding. The following main technology groups can be distinguished: Information and communication technologies or ICT in the study of the subject. The use of these technologies is associated with the development of the information society and the active introduction of the media in all spheres of life. Such technologies are aimed at informing the minds of students. Curricula include new disciplines in computer science, information processes, and ICT. The teaching process is also being actively informed to help improve the information culture of faculty and students; Person-centered technologies. These technologies are aimed at prioritizing the education and upbringing of the individual. The whole educational process is focused on the development of the individual, taking into account the individuality and developmental characteristics of the individual. Information and analytical support of the educational process. The use of this group of technologies is aimed at researching and adequately assessing the development of each student, classroom, parallel, educational institution; Intellectual development monitoring. The technologies are based on the use of graphs, a test system, new assessment methods that allow to monitor the developmental dynamics of individual students and the quality of education in general; Educational technologies. The learning process is inseparable from upbringing. Therefore, new ways of developing the individual, his basic qualities are being introduced; Didactic technologies. They are a key factor in the development of an educational institution. Such technologies are based on a set of techniques and tools that include the use of traditional and innovative technologies:

independent work with educational literature, audiovisual, multimedia, the use of differentiated teaching methods

Among the student-centered learning technologies, the following can be distinguished: Multilevel learning technology. According to this technology, the learning process is built according to the ability of each student to master the material, ie. each student is given time to master the program, which is exactly what he or she needs and responds to. Thus, the core of the curriculum is effectively mastered. Team learning technology of peers. This technology involves grouping students into groups of at least two people with psychological compatibility. They may have different levels of intellectual development, but they perform tasks, help each other, and thereby develop each other. It develops logical thinking, a sense of responsibility, adequate self-esteem and helps to liberate students. Technology of collaboration. This technology involves bringing students together in small communities and learning in them. Education should be done together with an understanding of each other's successes and failures. Education is based on the definition of common goals and objectives, the mandatory responsibility of each student and the provision of equal conditions for the effective acquisition of cognitive information. Innovations in education - the implementation of best pedagogical practices everything related. The educational process, which is at the forefront of modern science, is aimed at imparting knowledge, skills, abilities, personality, civic qualities to students. Changes depend on changes in attitudes towards time, learning, upbringing and development. Importance of innovation in education Innovative technologies in education Regulate education and direct it in the right direction allows People were always afraid of the unknown and new things, they were negative about any change. Stereotypes that exist in the public mind, affecting the usual way of life, lead to painful events, preventing the renewal of all forms of education. People accept innovations in modern education the reason he is reluctant to do so is by blocking vital needs for convenience, security, and self-affirmation. Not everyone is ready to re-learn theory, take an exam, change their mind, spend personal time and money. Once the update process has started, you can only stop it using special methods. Methods of Introducing Innovations: The most common ways to test the effectiveness of changes initiated in education are: The Document Marking Method. In order to evaluate innovations in the education system, the possibility of large-scale introduction of innovations into the educational process is limited. Individual school, university,

educational institution will be selected and based on them the experiment will be carried out. This implies the introduction of a separate new innovative element. □Eternal experience□ means evaluating the results obtained over a long period of time.The barrier of creativity. Teachers who are accustomed to working on old programs do not want to change, learn, and develop anything. They are hostile to all the innovations in the education system.Compliance. Flexibility, unwillingness to develop, fear of looking like a black sheep in the eyes of others, ridiculous appearance make teachers refuse to make unusual pedagogical decisions.Personal concern. Because of self-confidence, ability, strength, low self-esteem, and fear of expressing their opinions openly, many teachers resist any change in the educational institution to the last chance.Hardness of thinking. Old school teachers see their ideas as unique, final, irreconcilable. They do not strive to acquire new knowledge and skills, react negatively to new trends in modern educational institutions.

Conclusion:This article provides information on "Using modern innovations in the modern education system."

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